

EFFECTS OF VARIATION IN FEEDING FREQUENCY ON THE GROWTH AND SURVIVAL OF *CLARIAS GARIEPINUS* FINGERLINGS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the research was to determine the effects of feeding frequency on growth and survival of *Clarias gariepinus*. The feeding frequency ranged from once daily, twice daily, thrice daily to once in two days. The experiment was conducted for 56 days using one hundred and sixty fingerlings. The fingerlings were stocked equally in eight 30 litres plastic aquaria. A commercial feed (coppens) with nutritional status of crude protein 42%, crude fat 13%, crude fibre 3%, and ash 6.9% was used for the feeding. The fingerlings fed once daily had 20.15g and 15.35cm of the body weight (g) and length (cm) respectively but these were not significantly different from others (P 0.05). The fingerlings fed twice daily had the least mean weight and length but they are significantly difference from others (P 0.05). Highest specific growth rate (SGR), 2.37 was recorded in the fingerlings fed once daily. The final condition factor values of the fingerlings in each group of the experimented fingerlings were not significantly different (P 0.05). The fingerlings fed once in two days had the highest feed conversion ratio (FCR), 2.37 while the fingerlings fed once daily had the least value of 1.08. The least value was significantly different from others (P 0.05). Highest survival rate of 95% was recorded in the fingerlings fed once in two days, followed by those fed once daily with 92.5%. There was no significantly difference in the survival rate in the fingerlings fed once daily and those fed once in two days except those fed twice and thrice daily. The body composition of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings was greatly influenced by the different feeding regime. This research confirmed that feeding once a day greatly increase growth and survival of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings

KEYWORDS: Feeding, *Clarias gariepinus*. Fingerlings, Frequency

INTRODUCTION

Clarias belong to a genius of Catfish of the family *Clariidae*, the air breathing catfishes. The sharp tooth Catfish is a large eel – like fish, usually of dark grey or black colouration on the back, fading to a white belly. *Clarias gariepinus* is a nocturnal fish like many *Catfishes*; it feeds on living as well as dead animal matter. As a result of its wide mouth it is able to swallow relatively large prey whole. It has been reported to have swallowed large water birds such (Annop *et.al*, 2009). It crawls on dry ground to escape drying pools. The Catfish sometimes produces loud croaking sound, not unlike the voice of the crow. The rearing of the African Catfish in Africa started in the early seventies in central and Western Africa as it was realized that it was a very suitable species for aquaculture. It grows very fast and feeds on a large variety of agriculture by – products. It is hardy and can tolerate adverse water quality conditions. It can be raised in higher densities resulting in high net yields.

Good nutrition is one of the most important factors influencing the ability of cultured fish to exhibit its genetic potential for growth and reproduction. They are also greatly influenced by factors such as behaviour of fish, quality of feed, daily ratio size, feed intake or water temperature. Since the feed cost accounts approximately 40 – 60% of the operating costs in intensive culture system (Anderson,*et.al*. 1997, Craig and Heifrich, 2009). The food requirement of different species vary in quantity and quality according to the nature of the fish, its feeding habitat, its size, environment and its behavioural pattern and

reproductive rate. The development of new species – specific diet formulations supports the aquacultural system as it expands to satisfy the desire for affordable, save and high – quality fish and sea food products (Craig and Heifrich, 2009). Aquaculture has been the recognized as a means of increasing fish production in the developed and developing countries including Nigeria.

Clarias is a very popular fish species in Nigeria due to its culture characteristics which endeared it to many fish farmers. Ninety per cent of the Catfish supplied in Sub – Saharan Africa in the year 2000 was recorded in Nigeria (FAO,2004). In Nigeria, getting fast growing fish seed has been a major problem to fish farmers targeting high yields. It was noted that the largest matured *Clarias gariepinus* would usually gives the best spawn weight in induced breeding but there has not been any information on whether the fish with best spawn would equally give best fry survival and growth performance (Ufodike,1987) .

In Nigeria and other part of the world, studies have been conducted on the effects of feeding frequency on food consumption and growth of fish (Robinson and Li 2007, Odedeyi, 2007, Lee *et.al*, 1997). The authors observed that channel catfish feed daily (high frequency) consumed more feed with a resultant very high production when compared with fish that were feed at every other day (Robinson and Li, 2007). Based on the researches on the effects of feeding frequency on food intake and growth in edible fishes, limited information is available on feeding pattern of *Clarias gariepinus*. There is a need to study the effect of feeding frequency on the growth and survival of this important fish.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

One hundred and sixty – five hatchery bred fingerlings of African Catfish *Clarias gariepinus* were obtained from the Ministry Of Agriculture, Aquaculture Department Ado – Ekiti, Ekiti – state and brought to the postgraduate laboratory of the Department of Zoology, Ekiti – State University, Ado – Ekiti. The fingerlings whose mean weigh ranged from 4.13grammes to 5.35grammes, mean length range from 4.10cm to 4.30cm were allowed to acclimatize for two days before sorted into eight plastic aquaria. Each of the labeled aquaria which were grouped into four was stocked with twenty fingerlings. Before, the commencement of the feeding trial, the old uneaten feed was siphoned. The experimental fish were deprived of feed for 24 hours; the fish in the four groups were feed at different feeding frequencies. Those in aquaria A, B, C, and D were feed once, twice and thrice daily and the other aquarium fed once in two days. Fish were fed with commercial 4.0mm extruded coppen’s Catfish feed manufactured by Coppen’s international Helmond, Holland: Crude protein 40%, Crude fat 10%, Crude fiber 4.2%, Ash 7.7%. This feed was used through the trial. Mean daily consumption of feed (g) by each fish fingerlings per feed frequency was estimated by subtracting the weight of the uneaten feed from the total weight of feed given to the fish in each aquarium and dividing it by the total weight of feed given to the fish in each aquarium and dividing it by the total number of fingerlings in that aquarium. These values were then summed up to determine the weekly feed consumption per feeding frequency.

Because of the small sizes of the fingerlings all the fingerlings in each aquarium were collected in a Petri – dish and weighed collectively on weighing balance. The average weight in grammes was calculated to represent the weight of each individual fingerling. Total length of each fingerling was measured to the nearest 0.1mm using a plastic ruler.

Measurement of weights and lengths of the fingerlings was done once every week throughout the experimental period. From the data obtained during the periods, specific growth rates ($SGR = ((\ln W_t - \ln W_0)/t) \times 100$). Where W_t is the weight of the fish at time t , W_0 is the initial weight of the fish, and t is the culture period in days.

FCR = total dry diet fed (g)/ total weight gain (g) Coefficient of variability of the body weight on the initial (CV_{BW} and final CV_{bwf}) day of the experiment, $CV_{BW} \% = 100 (SD/BW)$

Condition coefficient, $K = 100 (BW) / TL^3$ where TL = total length

Statistical analysis of data was performed by one way ANOVA with Duncan test at the level of 95% using SPSS 16. Statistical significance was set at the level of $P < 0.05 \pm$ standard deviation. (SD).

RESULTS

Table1: Shows the mean weight (g) of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings fed with different daily feeding frequency for eight weeks. Feeding frequency was not found to have a significant effect on the growth rate of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings. By the end of second week of feeding trial, the fingerlings fed once daily with 7.93 ± 0.26 of body weight were significantly different from the fingerlings fed once in two days with 5.81 ± 0.57 of body weight ($P \leq 0.05$). Those fingerlings fed once were similar to fingerlings fed twice daily and those fed thrice daily. At the end of six weeks of feeding trial, the mean weight of the *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings feed once per day (14.05 ± 0.50) and those fed thrice per day (11.52 ± 1.13) were significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$) compared to the fingerlings fed twice daily and once in two days 9.70 ± 0.24 and 8.87 ± 1.05 respectively

At the end of eight weeks of feeding trials, the mean weights were not significantly different from each other ($P \leq 0.05$).

Table 2: Shows the mean length (cm) of *Clarias gariepinus* with different daily feeding frequency fed for eight weeks. The results corroborate what was obtained on the growth. At the end of eight weeks of feeding trials, there was no significant different ($p \leq 0.05$) in the length of the fingerlings in the entire feeding groups.

Table 3 shows the change in the mean growth rate, condition factors, survival, and specific growth rate (SGR) and feed conversion ratio of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings fed differently for eight weeks. The daily specific growth rate of fish feed once in two days (1.46 ± 1.30) was significantly lower compare to the fish fed once daily, twice daily and thrice daily ($2.37 \pm 0.16, 2.48 \pm 0.10$ and 2.29 ± 0.13 respectively). Significant highest weight gain (276.6 ± 23.76) was observed in fish fed once daily ($p \leq 0.05$) when compare to all other feeding regimes. The best food conversion ratio (2.37 ± 0.31) was observed in fish fed once in two days while the least food conversion ratio (1.08 ± 0.26) was observed in fish fed once daily whereas no significant differences were noticed in groups fed twice and thrice daily ($P \leq 0.05$). Survival rate was higher in the group of fish fed once in two days while the least survival rate was recorded in the group of fish fed twice daily. The condition factors in the fish were not significantly different from each other ($P \leq 0.05$). The final body weight coefficient of variation in the group of fish fed thrice daily (36.98 ± 4.20) was significantly higher than other groups, while the least values (4.57 ± 0.32) and 4.94 ± 0.76 were recorded in the groups of fish fed once daily and once in two days respectively.

DISCUSSION

Growth performance in *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings were assessed using data on weights and length measurements. Growth rate was higher in fingerlings fed once daily compared to that of fish fed twice daily, thrice daily and those fed once in two days, although the difference between the groups were not significant. The results obtained in this study showed that growth performance of African Catfish *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings can be significantly influenced by feeding regimes that strongly affect the feed ingestion and assimilation. The highest growth performance (Final mean weight, weight gain percentage and specific growth rate) were recorded in fingerlings fed once daily followed by thrice daily treatment.

Fish that were fed less frequently can adapt to such condition by consuming larger amount of feed during each feeding. If such a schedule is applied for a longer period, this can lead to increase gut capacity and to hyperphagia (abnormally large intake of solids by mouth due to excessive hunger)(Jobling,1983, Ruohonen and Grove,1996). Fish that are fed more frequently consume a large amount of feed however, when the intervals between meals are short, the food passes through the digestive tract more quickly, resulting in less effective digestion (Liu and Liao,1999). Hence, determine the optimum feeding frequency is of such practical importance to fish farmers and Scientists. Optimum feeding frequency for maximum growth of fish is basically in fish size, age and culture conditions including water temperature, feed quality and amount of feed provided (Verreth and Eding, 1993, Lee, *et.al.*2000)

A review of the literature indicates that the effect of feeding frequency on fish growth varies considerably. In order to provide for the maximum growth rate in Salmonids, one to three ratios daily are sufficient to feed them (Ruohonen *et.al* 1998) . Observation on milkfish, *Chanos chanos*, showed that the best growth performance was recorded in fingerlings fed twice daily than fish fed (Testiima *et. al.*1984). [16]reported that feeding estuarine grouper *Epinephelus tauvina*, once every other day resulted in optimal growth, while weight gains were reduced in fish fed every 3, 4 or 5 days. In hybrid sunfish, fish fed once daily were smaller than the one fed 2, 3, or 4 times per day, however, there were differences among the latter three feeding frequencies. The closed related African Catfish species, *Clarias lazera*, achieved the maximum growth when fed constantly (Hogendoorn), 1981). It was reported that Catfish, *Heterobranchus longifilis* fed twice daily higher percentage weight gains, SGR and average final weight compare to fish feed once per day, once an alternate day (Davies *,et.al.* 2006). However, a decrease in feeding frequency improved the growth rate of rainbow trout. A study conducted by (Alanara, 1992) showed that the frequent use of automatic feeder had a negative effect on rainbow trout. This species exhibits a rapid increase in activity during feeding; this may suggest that frequent feeding is a stress factor that elicits great expenditure of energy thus reducing the fish growth.

The *Clarias gariepinus* fed twice daily followed by those fed once in two days and thrice daily reportedly had low food conversion ratio (FCR). The *Clarias* fed once daily had the best FCR value and this is significantly different from all other treatments. The results obtained in this work indicated that catfish fed more frequently might utilize diet loss efficient than fish fed frequently. According to (Webster, *et. al.*, 2001), Channel Catfish fed once daily or twice daily had similar food conversion ratio values. The feeding frequency had little effect on food conversion ratio (Anderson *et. al.*, 1997). This may reflect that the food consumption is the growth limiting factor. It was observed in some fish species that the greater the food intake, the greater the growth response. This was the expectation since a high amount of nutrients become available to fish when the fish are fed more often. Studies conducted on some other fish species have shown that feed consumption and growth generally increased with feeding frequency up to a given limit (Wang *et.al.*,1994).

The feeding frequency had a significant effect on the body weight variability and this was the characteristics of each group. Therefore, the average value of the coefficient (CVBW) differs significantly. In a study conducted by (Jobling, 1993) on the feeding frequency of Arctic charr, showed that decreasing feeding frequency of fish kept at reduced stocking densities lowered the body growth rate and increase intra – group body weight variability. The application of a high stocking density reduced the level of antagonistic behaviour which led to more effective feeding. In this research, highest survival rates were

recorded in the fingerlings fed once in two days and once daily while the low survival rate was recorded in fingerlings fed twice and thrice daily. The reason for this may be as a result of too much of waste feed in the aquaria due to excess feeding. This adversely affect the water quality and might leads to their loss appetite by not responding to feeding, low aggressive behaviour and high mortality in the twice and thrice daily feeding frequency groups.

This study also suggests that body composition of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings is affected significantly by the frequency of feeding. The increase in the crude protein of the entire fish sample might be indicative of the adequacy of the high crude protein level of the feed used and protein intake by the fish. This means that the experimental fish converted and utilized protein from feed into their body protein. (Jobling, 1983) reported that increase lipids levels in channel catfish fed twice daily compare to fish fed once daily, Webster *et. al.* (2001) observed no significant differences in percentage moisture, protein and lipids in fillet of channel catfish fed either once or twice daily. It has been shown that low body lipid content of fish resulted from their decline feeding (Liu and Liao, 1999). The ability of an organism to utilize nutrients especially protein will positively influence its growth rate (Sogbesan and Ugwumba, 2008) . This suggests that fish must have efficiency converted feed consumed to growth. Efficient production and growth of fish depend on feeding the best possible diets at level not exceeding the dietary needs (Charles, *et,al.* 1984). In fish culture practices, studies on the amount and frequency of feeding are aimed at identifying the optimum levels of both. Increase feed digestibility and increased water quality are the benefits of using the correct feeding frequency. Two or three feeding a day have been found to be sufficient for maximum growth of a number of different fish species (Ruohonen, *et.al.*1998). Based on the results obtained in this study, the growth and survival of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings. It is therefore recommended that *C. gariepinus* fingerlings should be feed once daily for maximum growth and better survival.

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TABLE 1: Changes in weight of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings fed with different daily feeding for period of eight (8) weeks.
 NO OF WEEK
 Mean values in the same row with the same superscripts are not significantly different (p = 0.05).

Daily feeding frequency	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Fed once daily	5.35a ± (0.09)	6.30a ± (0.01)	7.93a ± (0.26)	8.38ab ± (0.26)	9.79a ± (0.45)	11.5a ± (0.35)	14.05a ± (0.50)	19.85a ± (1.06)	20.15a ± (0.92)
Fed twice daily	4.90a ± (0.03)	5.84a ± (0.01)	6.94ab ± (0.28)	7.21bc ± (0.69)	7.45ab ± (0.28)	8.49ab ± (1.16)	9.70bc ± (0.24)	10.34a ± (1.78)	11.10a ± (1.27)
Fed thrice daily	4.76a ± (0.38)	5.88a ± (0.27)	7.24ab ± (0.28)	8.70a ± (0.78)	9.50a ± (0.99)	10.52ab ± (1.16)	11.52ab ± (0.24)	15.50a ± (4.95)	17.20a ± (6.36)
Fed once in two days	4.13a ± (1.34)	5.05a ± (1.32)	5.81b ± (0.57)	6.25c ± (0.66)	6.28c ± (1.02)	7.47b ± (0.63)	8.87c ± (1.05)	12.48a ± (0.68)	12.95a ± (0.64)

Table 2: Changes in length of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings fed with different daily feed frequency for period of eight (8) weeks.

Daily feeding frequency	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Fed once daily	5.64a ± (0.13)	7.54a ± (0.04)	9.87a ± (0.00)	11.35a ± (0.07)	11.60a ± (0.00)	12.20a ± (0.14)	13.25a ± (0.00)	14.10a ± (0.00)	15.35a ± (0.07)
Fed twice daily	5.32ab ± (0.11)	7.30a ± (0.33)	8.74b ± (0.40)	10.65b ± (0.07)	10.70b ± (0.00)	11.10bc ± (0.00)	11.50ab ± (0.42)	11.83a ± (1.41)	12.15a ± (1.20)
Fed thrice dilly	5.39ab ± (0.16)	6.72b ± (0.11)	9.30ab ± (0.28)	10.75ab ± (0.50)	10.90b ± (0.28)	11.30b ± (0.42)	11.90ab ± (0.99)	12.50a ± (0.42)	13.75a ± (1.77)
Fed once in two days	4.95b ± (0.16)	6.72b ± (0.11)	8.67b ± (0.13)	9.80c ± (0.08)	10.00c ± (0.00)	10.35c ± (0.35)	10.75b ± (0.21)	11.80a ± (0.42)	12.55a ± (0.50)

Mean Values in t same row with the same superscript are not significantly different (p > 0.05).

Table 3: Changes in growth, condition factor of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings fed at different frequencies for a period of eight (8) weeks.
FEEDING EXPERIMENTAL GROUPS

Specification	Fed once daily	Fed twice daily	Fed thrice daily	Fed once in two days
Initial mean body weight (g)	5.35 ± (0.09)	4.90a ± (0.03)	4.76a ± (0.38)	4.13a ± (1.34)
Final mean body weight (g)	20.15a± (0.92)	11.10 ±(1.27)	17.20a ± (6.36)	12.94a ± (0.64)
Mean weight gained (g)	14.80± (1.04)	8.38b ±(1.97)	12.44a ± (6.75)	6.20c ± (1.30)
Specific growth rate SGR %	2.37a ± (0.16)	2.048a ± 90.100	2.29A ± (0.13)	1.46B ± (0.07)
Wet weight gain (%)	276.64a ± (23.76)	213.94c ± (12.46)	261.34b ± (18.35)	126.53d ± (9.68)
Initial condition factor	2.98ab ± (0.04)	3.25a ± (0.05)	3.04ab ± (0.07)	3.41a ± (0.01)

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